

ADDITIONAL PROTECTION DEVICE FOR GRID INVERTER OF PHOTOVOLTAIC STATION

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In the course of studying the problems of electricity quality in a low-voltage distribution network, an analysis of waveforms describing voltages, currents and frequency was used. The archive of network inverters of a photovoltaic plant connected in parallel to a low-voltage distribution network during operation has also been analyzed.

On January 24-25, 2023, experimental studies were conducted to measure the voltage values of each phase in the low-voltage distribution network of the Faculty of Energy Engineering of Tashkent State Technical University. The voltage, current, and frequency waveforms were recorded using a two-channel FNIRSI -1013D type flat oscilloscope.

The following advantages have been identified in the proposed development: it prevents the occurrence of burns and fires caused by overheating of the mains inverter in PVS with low-quality electricity in the local electric grid. The total weight of the development is light, it works without noise, and the cost is very low. There is access to purchase electrical elements and parts in the domestic market of Uzbekistan.

Additional protective equipment is intended for:

- a. control of the permissible voltage level;
- b. control of the correct alternation and absence of phase sticking;
- c. control of the full-phase and symmetry of the mains voltage (phase misalignment);
- d. disconnecting the load at low-quality mains voltage;
- e. quality control of the mains voltage after disconnecting the inverter and automatically switching it on after restoring voltage parameters;
- f. Emergency indications in case of an emergency and indication of the presence of voltage in each phase. The development also performs zero control by an indirect method .

In the world, special importance is attached to the issues of electricity generation based on low-power photovoltaic plants and their integration into a low-voltage distribution grid for energy supply to consumers.

The conducted studies allowed us to evaluate the quality of electrical energy in the low-voltage distributed electric grid of Uzbekistan. Based on the results obtained, it can be analyzed that the values of the voltage deviation of each phase in a low-voltage electrical grid are much greater than the nominal value in winter and summer. The voltage deviation of each phase in the low-voltage electrical network and their values, respectively, were $\delta U_{m(-)}^A - 7,8\%$, $\delta U_{m(-)}^B - 20\%$ и $\delta U_{m(-)}^C - 20\%$ in winter conditions the period in Tashkent. Numerous studies have been conducted on the archives of grid inverters of various types for PVS integrated into the low-voltage electric grid, which are installed in the regions of the country. Data from the memory archive of

the grid inverter shows that the reason for frequent disconnection and connection of the inverter to the electrical grid are the following main factors: not phase stability of voltage; losses in the electrical grid; improper grounding of the inverter, etc. Additional protective equipment has been developed and created for PVS inverters integrated with a low-voltage electrical network characterized by reliability, automation and resistance to the thermal condition of heated nodes.